

INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation

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Key words: interactive, process,behaviour,discipline,approach,method,participants, knowledge.

OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA PEDAGOGIK JARAYONNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INTERFAOL TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI

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Annotation

Maqolada kattalarning kasbiy rivojlanishi shaxsiy rivojlanishdan ajralmasdir.Kasbiy faoliyat sub'ekti sifatida shakllanib,o'ziga bajaruvchi sifatida munosabatni shakllantirgan holda, shaxs shaxs sifatida rivojlanadi shaxs dastlabki ma'lumotlarni turli tomonlardan tahlil qilish, asosiy narsani ta'kidlash, umumlashtirish qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi. tasvirlarning turli xil xayoliy o'zgarishlarini amalga oshiring, fikrlashning ijodiy yo'nalishi shakllanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv, jarayon,xulq-atvor,intizom,yondashuv,usul,Partik shimlar, bilim.

Professional development of an adult is inseparable from personal development - these are two interrelated and complementary processes. Forming as a subject of professional activity and forming an attitude towards oneself as a doer, a person develops as a person. Professional development is one of the forms of personality development.Interactive play is an active learning method based on the

experience gained as a result of special organized social interaction of participants in order to change the individual behavior model, that is, these are methods that organize the process of social interaction on the basis of which the participants develop a kind of "new" knowledge, born directly in the course of this process, or a result of it. These games are most often used to teach students. Currently, there is a need to introduce new approaches to the study of general technical disciplines, the introduction of new educational technologies in teaching engineering graphics, in particular. This is due to many reasons. First of all, the lack of motivation among students for the chosen specialty or profession, a vague idea of that, where the knowledge gained in the study of this discipline will be useful. In search of ways to solve the problem of enhancing cognitive activity, research and search methods, non-standard forms of conducting classes, didactic games, etc. are used in the classroom. Such training is called interactive.

In engineering graphics classes, various types of student activities are used: individual, work in pairs, micro-groups. Work in microgroups is carried out on the themes of mechanical engineering drawing: "Connections of parts", "Views, cuts, sections". "Assembly drawings". This type of activity allows students to deeply study topics and acquire valuable skills for working in a team:

- form their own point of view, argue and defend it correctly:
- carry out communication in the course of professional activity, including the exchange of information:
- develop a unified strategy of interaction, listen and evaluate opponents, obey the decision:
- be responsible for the results of their activities. Teaching in small groups forms students' independence of thinking, develops intellectual and creative skills.

Using interactive teaching while sketching and exploring the topic "Detailing". the student to a greater extent becomes the subject of learning, enters into a dialogue with the teacher, performs creative, problematic tasks.

When using the interactive teaching methodology on the topic "Detailing" occurs:

1. forming, which is associated with mental actions characteristic of visual perception of a graphic image on a plane (specially selected tasks that students performed on a computer):
2. formation, which occurs in the process of practical constructions on the plane;

3. formation, which is associated with the visual perception of a graphic image, while mental and objective actions occur in three-dimensional space.

In the course of detailing, you can solve tasks for the formation of graphic skills (display lines, apply dimensions, build the contours of flat images, etc.). on the development of mental actions (comparing images. reading drawings. building images. imaginary transformations of images, etc.).

Graphic tasks contribute to the solid assimilation of knowledge, they are a means of forming graphic skills, control of knowledge, skills and abilities. In addition, they have great opportunities for the mental development of students.

They imply not a mechanical application of the learned rules, but an independent search for ways to solve some problems - the choice of the main type, the number of images, the use of the necessary conventional images, symbols, and the like. The process of solving such problems is an important means of developing thinking. The personality develops the ability to analyze initial data from different angles, to highlight the main thing, to generalize. make various imaginary transformations of images, a creative direction of thinking is formed.

Interactive activity in the course of detailing involves dialogue, communication between students. Consequently, such an organization and development of dialogue communication leads to mutual understanding, mutual actions, to the joint solution of common, but significant for each student, tasks. Graphic skills are formed, and also during the dialogue, students learn to think critically, solve complex problems based on an analysis of circumstances and relevant information, make thoughtful decisions, participate in discussions, communicate with other people.

With the help of a set of methodological techniques, students are led to the need to implement a whole chain of mental transformations, learn to see with their mind's eye, make mental turns of images created in the imagination, which are then embodied in a plane with the help of integrative learning. The use of interactive teaching methods forms students' motivation for learning and interest in future professional activities.

The result of a well-organized and effectively conducted interactive method can be a change in the perception of the participants, which leads to a quick, immediate solution or a new understanding of an existing problem. In this case, the emergence of such a new understanding is facilitated by immersion in the process of interaction, which makes it possible to explore the problem from the inside, to pass it through "oneself" to analyze one's own behavior and to draw the necessary conclusions.

List of used literature:

1. Stupina. S. B. Technologies of interactive learning in higher education [Text]: a teaching aid / S. B. Stupin. - Saratov. 2009.
2. Ekzhanova E.A. Fundamentals of Integrated Learning: A Manual for Universities M. 2008.
3. Ivanova - Komarschuk A. The usefulness of interactive teaching methods [Electronic resource] [http: y / osvita.ua / teclmol / 6564](http://y/osvita.ua/teclmol/6564).
4. Technique for teaching drawing. Ed. E.A. Vaselenko M-1990